

Challenges and Problems of Software Processes in the Context of Global Software Development: A Systematic Mapping Study

Extraction Forms

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: DISTRIBUTED REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION: MINIMIZING THE EFFECT OF GEOGRAPHIC DISPERSION</p> <p>Author(s): Leandro Lopes, Rafael Prikladnicki, Jorge L. N. Audy, Azriel Majdenbaum</p> <p>Publication date: 2004</p> <p>Source: ICEIS 2004 - Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems</p>
Information from RQ1: What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems:In geographically distributed environment (physical and temporal distance, cultural differences, trust, communication)</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Geographically distributed environment</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through a case study study was conducted in a multinational organization with software development units distributed globally.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: The next research step involves the validation of the proposed process.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Customising software products in distributed software development A model for allocating customisation requirements across organizational boundaries Author(s): Abdulrahman M. Qahtani, Gary B. Wills, Andrew M. Gravell Publication date: 2013 Source: International Conference on Information Society, i-Society 2013</p>
Information from RQ1: What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Communicating and allocating customisation requirements across distributed organizational boundaries. Approach challenges/problems: Communicating customisation requirements</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>Through a survey of 19 professionals, which confirmed that communicating customisation requirements in a DSD context is a significant challenge.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES, SurveyGizmo (which was used to design, distribute and administer the survey) and SPSS, for analysis of data. <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: After 19 participants answered the form, a so-called One Sample T-test was performed on the data, using the data analytic tool SPSS.</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Distributed Requirements Elicitation Using a Spatial Hypertext Wiki Author(s): Carlos Solís, Nour Ali Publication date: 08/2010 Source: 2010 5th IEEE International Conference Global Software Engineering (ICGSE)</p>
Information from RQ1: What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Provide integrated collaborative tools that implement creativity techniques to externalize, share and store knowledge in a common repository and coordination over distance. Approach challenges/problems: Creativity in the RE process</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>Analyzing the context of Requirements Elimination and understanding the problems that occur during this phase.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Spatial Hypertext Wiki <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES - <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The proposal was validated through a table, comparing the functionalities of the proposed tool with other similar tools. In addition, the team continues to perform tests to verify usability.</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Cultural Patterns in Software Process Mishaps: Incidents in Global Projects Author(s): Eve MacGregor, Yvonne Hsieh, Philippe Kruchten Publication date: 2005 Source: Proceedings of the 2005 Workshop on Human and Social Factors of Software Engineering, HSSE 2005</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Cross-cultural sensitivity, challenges in mediated communication, planning and management of global innovation, differences in work-style, power, hierarchy and agency.</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Intercultural issues in GSD.</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>Through anthropological research on the concept of culture and the analysis of how it is included in GSD.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES - <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The validation of the research will be through a questionnaire to obtain external data. The questionnaire will address several points considered key to understanding the life cycle of GSD and verifying what is really happening during the process.</p>

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Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Why the Development Outcome Does Not Meet the Product Owners' Expectations?</p> <p>Author(s): Timo O. A. Lehtinen, Ville Tomi Heikkila, Risto Virtanen, Juha Itkonen</p> <p>Publication date: 2015</p> <p>Source: Springer International Publishing</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Incompatibility between customer expectations and software development results</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Incompatibility between customer expectations and software development results</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through a case study on the problems in the collaboration between Product Owners (PO) and software development teams in a large distributed Scrum organization
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - ARCA tool, cause-effect diagram</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: The data analysis was carried out with the company representatives.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Towards a unified tool for collaborative software engineering projects Author(s): Amal Rochd, Maria Zrikem, Abdeslam Jakjoud, Claude Baron Publication date: 11/2015 Source: 2015 Third World Conference on Complex Systems (WCCS)</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Managing concurrent and collaborative engineering. Approach challenges/problems: Impact of coordination and collaboration on project efficiency.</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Observing the context and evolution of software engineering and analyzing the success and failure rates of projects.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES COLlaborative Software Engineering Framework <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES - <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: Validate the effectiveness of the solution through a case study, showing how a classical and the collaboration process can be expressed in terms of COLSEF metamodel.</p>

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Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: In-Time Role-Specific Notification as Formal Means to Balance Agile Practices in Global Software Development Settings</p> <p>Author(s): Wahyudin, Dindin and Heindl, Matthias and Eckhard, Benedikt and Schatten, Alexander and Biffel, Stefan</p> <p>Publication date: 2008</p> <p>Source: Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Keep all members aware of all project-related changes, dosing the information depending on the role</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Communication between members of the same project.</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through the analysis of the agile practices used in GSD.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: An earlier study on the feasibility of plug-in support for the integrated impact analysis tool was conducted to compare the approach with other alternatives, looking at the method used by Siemens PSE to evaluate the performance of each alternative.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A Block-chain Oriented Model Driven Framework for handling Inconsistent Requirements in Global Software Development</p> <p>Author(s): Nayab Gull, Muhammad Rashid, Farooque Azam, Yawar Rasheed, Muhammad Waseem Anwar</p> <p>Publication date: 2021-02-23</p> <p>Source: 2021 10th International Conference on Software and Computer Applications</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Communication gap between the dispersed stakeholders</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Communication gap between the dispersed stakeholders</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through the analysis of the problem and the understanding that there is still no model capable of meeting the needs of geographically dispersed teams.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Blockchain Oriented Model (BOMO) and a graphical modeling tool using Sirius.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: The validity occurred through a case study and it was confirmed that the proposed framework can be used with confidence and can be modified to meet inconsistent requirements in a promising way.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A Competence-based View on the Global Software Development Process</p> <p>Author(s): Philipp Holtkamp, Jan Martin Pawlowski</p> <p>Publication date: 2015</p> <p>Source: Journal of Universal Computer Science</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: The distance temporal, geographical and sociocultural</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Competence-related challenges.</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through literature review and related research on the subject
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't validate.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A Decision Support System for Global Software Development Author(s): Sarah Beecham, John Noll, Ita Richardson, Deepak Dhungana Publication date: 08/2011 Source: 2011 IEEE Sixth International Conference on Global Software Engineering Workshop</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: global distance, temporal distance and linguistic and cultural distance. Approach challenges/problems: global distance</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	From a study on information overload and decision-making at GSD
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Global Teaming Decision Support System <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: Through a questionnaire to reflect each of the requirements of the GT-DSS described, focusing on the usability and usefulness of the tool.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A Method for the Identification of Logical Dependencies Author(s): Gustavo Ansaldi Oliva, Marco Aurélio Gerosa Publication date: 08/2012 Source: 2012 IEEE Seventh International Conference on Global Software Engineering Workshops</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Finding more adequate ways to group related commits and to filter out irrelevant dependencies Approach challenges/problems: logical dependencies</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through the analysis of bibliographic references that investigate projects in GSD.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: The preliminary evaluation of the method by running it on the code repository of the Apache Software Foundation code repository

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A method for work distribution in Global Software Development Author(s): Dilani Wickramaarachchi, Richard Lai Publication date: 02/2013 Source: 2013 3rd IEEE International Advance Computing Conference (IACC)</p>
Infomation from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: distribution of work to multiple locations, minimize the additional costs and maximize the benefit Approach challenges/problems: distribution of work to multiple locations</p>
Infomation from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>Through the analysis of researches that point out that the main current challenge of GSD is to minimize the threats so that they can increase the probability of profits being high.</p>
Infomation from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p>() YES (x) NO</p>
Infomation from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p>() YES (x) NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Infomation from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The next research step involves the validation of the proposed process.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A multivocal study to improve the implementation of global requirements change management process: A client-vendor prospective</p> <p>Author(s): Muhammad Azeem Akbar, Sajjad Mahmood, Ahmed Alsanad, Abeer Abdul-Aziz Alsanad, Abdu Gumaei, Syed Furqan Qadri</p> <p>Publication date: 01/2020</p> <p>Source: Journal of Software: Evolution and Process</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Requirements changes in the software development process</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Requirements change management (RCM)</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through multivocal literature review and a questionnaire survey study to identify the success factors of RCM
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Google Forms</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: By conducting an empirical study with change management specialists</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A Process Framework for Global Software Engineering Teams Author(s): Ita Richardson, Valentine Casey , Fergal McCaffery, John Burton, Sarah Beecham Publication date: 11/2012 Source: Information and Software Technology</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Temporal, cultural, geographical and linguistic distance Approach challenges/problems: Temporal, cultural, geographical and linguistic distance</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Realizing that there are no frameworks that explicitly address the complex and changing needs of GSD
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Global Teaming Model <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The informal validation was done with the help of feedback given by experts from companies in the area, and the formal validation will be done through a Decision Support System (DSS) that they are developing.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A Proposal of an Ontology-Based System for Distributed Teams Author(s): Rodrigo G. C. Rocha, Ryan Azevedo, Silvio Meira Publication date: 8/2014 Source: 2014 40th EUROMICRO Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA)</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Inefficient communication between distributed team members, diverging cultures and high complexity or lack of project management Approach challenges/problems: Inexistence of a formal normalized model of a project's data and artifacts accessible to all the individuals involved.</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through a systematic review and the conclusion that there is no formal standardization model for a project's data and artifacts that is accessible to all individuals involved.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - DKDOnto <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: The proposed ontology has not yet been populated, so no testing or validation has been done.

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A Study on Global Software Development (GSD) and Software Development Processes in Malaysian Software Companies Author(s): Asif R. Khan, R. Akbar, D. W. H. Ten Publication date: Source: Journal of Telecommunication, Electronic and Computer Engineering</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Issues related to the globalization of IT and the way in which companies need to adapt to remain competitive in the marketplace. Approach challenges/problems: Software processes currently used by companies in Malaysia and how they will change after GSD</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>Through a study conducted in Malaysian companies.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Management methodologies such as SCRUM and XP <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The data was collected through interviews, but it is not explicit how it was analyzed or validated.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: A Systematic Study to Improve the Requirements Engineering Process in the Domain of Global Software Development</p> <p>Author(s): MUHAMMAD AZEEM AKBAR, AHMED ALSANAD, SAJJAD MAHMOOD, ABEER ABDULAZIZ ALSANAD, ABDO GUMAEI</p> <p>Publication date: 03/2020</p> <p>Source: IEEE Access</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Barriers to the requirements engineering RE process faced during GSD</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Barriers to the requirements engineering RE process faced during GSD</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through a study on why companies are outsourcing their services.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Google Forms to support search.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The research participants were selected through the snowball strategy, which is extremely efficient for collecting data in a dispersed and targeted manner. The data will be validated by experts</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: An Integrated Approach of Software Development and Test Processes to Distributed Teams Author(s): Gislaine Camila Lapasini Leal, Ana Paula Chave, Elisa Hatsue Moriya Huzita, Marcio Eduardo Delamaro Publication date: 11/12 Source: Journal of Universal Computer Science,</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Temporal distance, geographical dispersion and sociocultural differences Approach challenges/problems: Temporal distance, geographical dispersion and sociocultural differences</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through understanding how globalization has affected GSD.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Gnuplot 4.0 graphical tool. SPEM (notation is based on UML and therefore modeling the same diagrams that are used to model software) <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: 12 participants answer the questionnaire and profile Interviewees Feasibility Study

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Analytic hierarchy process-based prioritization framework for vendor's reliability challenges in global software development Author(s): Abdul Wahid Khan, Muhammad Zamir Publication date: 03/2021 Source: Journal of Software: Evolution and Process</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: communication and coordination problems, trust between both parties, time zone difference, poor contract management, knowledge management, cultural and linguistic issues Approach challenges/problems: Capability, reliance, delivery, management, and distinction</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>Through knowledge of the area and the existing problems.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Analytic hierarchy process (AHP) <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: Validated using a questionnaire.</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Are the expected benefits of requirements reuse hampered by distance? An experiment Author(s): Juan M. Carrillo de Gea, Joaquín Nicolás, José L. Fernández-Alemán, Ambrosio Toval, Ali Idri Publication date: 12/2016 Source: SpringerPlus</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Knowledge management, configuration management, cultural differences, communication, etc. Approach challenges/problems: Requirements reuse in GSD</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through research and systematic reviews on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Goal/Question/Metric (GQM) framework <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The study was conducted in an educational context, so as close as the study was to reality, it cannot be guaranteed that the objects studied represent the real world. But statistical tests were conducted with the students.</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Decision support for global software development with pattern discovery Author(s): JackH.C. Wu, Jacky Keung Publication date: 8/2016 Source: 2016 7th IEEE International Conference on Software Engineering and Service Science (ICSESS)</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Challenges to software project leaders/managers because of the multi-site, multi-cultural distributed environment which increases management difficulty Approach challenges/problems: Increase in management difficulty</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>Through research and studies on the subject.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: Not yet validated</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: DKD-S: An Ontology-based Tool for Global Software Development Author(s): Rodrigo Rocha, Renan Leandro, Israel Silva, Jean Araujo, Danillo Bion, Fred Freitas, Diogo Cordeiro, Arthur Gomes, Ryan Azevedo Publication date: 23/06/2021 Source: 2021 16th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI)</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: A lack of a formal and normalized model of a software project's data, and artifacts available in a coherent and easy access way for all members involved Approach challenges/problems: A lack of a formal and normalized model of a software project's data, and artifacts available in a coherent and easy access way for all members involved</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through research and discovery that there is no formal model that facilitates communication and understanding of what is going on in the project between members.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - DKD-S, Grails, Google Web Toolkit, Jena, Protegé, DKDOnto <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: The PUPO tool, is used to validate all the information answered by the DKD-S, checking its inferences, results, and presenting true data.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: DKDs: An ontology-based system for distributed teams Author(s): Rodrigo G. C. Rocha, Ryan Azevedo, Dimas Cassimiro, Ana Raquel Morais, Marcos P. Duarte, Silvio Meira Publication date: 2014 Source: Proceedings of the International Conference on Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering, SEKE</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Inexistence of a formal, normalized model of a project's data and artifacts accessible to all the individuals involved, which makes it harder for them to communicate Approach challenges/problems: Inexistence of a formal, normalized model of a project's data and artifacts accessible to all the individuals involved, which makes it harder for them to communicate</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - DKDOnto, DKDs <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: Validations are planned for future work, when the ontology is populated with real data.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Eleggua: An Event Infrastructure for Application Cooperation. Author(s): Rubby Casallas, Nicolas Lopez, Dario Correal Publication date: 01/2005 Source: Component-Oriented Enterprise Applications, Proceedings of the Conference on Component-Oriented Enterprise Applications (COEA 2005), Erfurt, Germany, 20 September 2005</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Geographical dispersion, processes coordination. Approach challenges/problems: Problems caused by geographical dispersion.</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through studies and finding a way to minimize the effects caused by geographical dispersion.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Eleggua <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: They are currently validating the infrastructure in a pilot project in a real-world GSD context to support a software testing and defect handling process.</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Enabling GSD Task Allocation via Cloud-based Software Processes Author(s): Sami Alajrami, Barbara Gallina, Alexander Romanovsky Publication date: 10/2017 Source: International Journal of Networked and Distributed Computing</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Project management because of geographical, time and cultural distances. Approach challenges/problems: Management challenges</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>By studying the area and recognizing the problems.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - SDaaS <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: They didn't validate.</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Global software development projects in one of the biggest companies in Latvia: is geographical distribution a problem? Author(s): Darja Smite Publication date: 01/2006 Source: Software Process: Improvement and Practice</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Organizational and cultural differences, language and time zone differences, lack of personal contact, and troubled communication over geographical distances Approach challenges/problems: Issues with project management and overall project performance</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>After research and realizing that there are no works that answer the questions about how to act in a distributed environment.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The data collected through forms is insufficient for analysis.</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Global Software Engineering: A Software Process Approach Author(s): Ita Richardson, Valentine Casey, John Burton e Fergal McCaffery Publication date: 04/2010 Source: Collaborative Software Engineering</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Temporal, cultural and geographic distance Approach challenges/problems: global distance</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>Through research on virtual development teams.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Global Teaming Process. <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: They didn't mention it</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: GSEPIM: A roadmap for software process assessment and improvement in the domain of global software development Author(s): Arif Ali Khan, Jacky Keung, Mahmood Niazi, Shahid Hussain, Mohammad Shameem Publication date: 01/2019 Source: Journal of Software: Evolution and Process</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: The lack of efficient organization of the development process development process Approach challenges/problems: The lack of efficient organization of the development process development process</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through the study and systematic review on the topic
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - GSEMPIM <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: Validations will be done empirically in future work

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: How do newcomers learn work process in global software development (GSD)?: a survey study from the perspective of newly project leaders Author(s): Raquel F. V. Cunha, Fernanda B. S. Souza, Franciney O. Lima, Bruno A. Bonifacio Publication date: 26/06/2020 Source: ICGSE '20: 15th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Global Software Engineering</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: knowledge transfer Approach challenges/problems: knowledge transfer</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Wiki <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: To collect the data, an internal survey was conducted to understand the level of approval of the technology used and later, the result is analyzed graphically. But it is not mentioned how this data is validated.</p>

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	Title of document: The impact of feedback in the global software process Author(s): M.M. Lehman, J.F. Ramil Publication date: 4/1999 Source: Journal of Systems and Software
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	GSD challenges/problems: Difficulties in achieving major improvements and maintenance in the GSD process Approach challenges/problems: Difficulties in achieving major improvements and maintenance in the GSD process
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through a review of the problems and issues behind GSD
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - FEAST <input type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Improving Global Software Development Project Performance Using Simulation Author(s): Siri-on Setamanit, Wayne Wakeland, David Raffol Publication date: 08/2007 Source: PICMET '07 - 2007 Portland International Conference on Management of Engineering & Technology</p>
<p>Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?</p>	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Geographic dispersion, time-zone differences as well as cultural and language differences. Approach challenges/problems: Geographic dispersion, time-zone differences as well as cultural and language differences.</p>
<p>Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?</p>	<p>I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.</p>
<p>Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Model used in this study is a hybrid model combining system dynamics (SD) and discrete-event (DES) paradigms. <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
<p>Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
<p>Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?</p>	<p>Evaluation description: For validation, Schlesinger [39] and Pegden [35] techniques were used</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Multilevel Ontology Framework for Improving Requirements Change Management in Global Software Development</p> <p>Author(s): ABEER ABDULAZIZ ALSANA, AZEDDINE CHIKH, ABDULRAHMAN MIRZA</p> <p>Publication date: 2019</p> <p>Source: IEEE Access</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Quality of requirements change management (RCM)</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Quality of requirements change management (RCM)</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>By studying the RCM and a comparison of the proposals made to minimize the effect on GSD.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Protegé, Multilevel Ontology Framework</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: The validation of the framework was done in the two ways most often cited in the literature, which are: questionnaires and case studies.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Overview of communication in global software development process</p> <p>Author(s): Shujian Wu</p> <p>Publication date: 07/2012</p> <p>Source: Proceedings of 2012 IEEE International Conference on Service Operations and Logistics, and Informatics</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Distance, time-zone differences, cultural differences, low trust, and language difference.</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Distance, time-zone differences, cultural differences, low trust, and language difference.</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - IBM Lotus products, BSCW (Basic Support for Cooperative Work) system, SharePoint, Groove, GroupSystems, SourceForge, SourceCast, and Rational Suite Enterprise.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Patternizing GSD Research: Maintainable Decision Support for Global Software Development Author(s): John Noll, Ita Richardson, Sarah Beecham Publication date: 8/2014 Source: 2014 IEEE 9th International Conference on Global Software Engineering</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: GSD Management Approach challenges/problems: GSD Management</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - DSS from the Global Teaming Model <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: Validation will take place in future work.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Review of global software development (GSD) trends in Malaysia and future directions</p> <p>Author(s): Asif Riaz Khan, Rehan Akbar, Doris Wong Hooi Ten, Mobashar Rehman, Kiran Adnan</p> <p>Publication date: 4/2017</p> <p>Source: 2017 IEEE Symposium on Computer Applications & Industrial Electronics (ISCAIE)</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: communication, collaboration, coordination, temporal and cultural distance, misunderstanding of requirements, mismatched practices, management issues and time-zone difference</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Communication</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Simulating Global Software Development Processes for Use in Education: A Feasibility Study</p> <p>Author(s): Miguel J. Monasor, Aurora Vizcaíno, Mario Piattini, John Noll and Sarah Beecham</p> <p>Publication date: 2013</p> <p>Source: Systems, Software and Services Process Improvement</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Cultural, linguistic and procedural problems procedural GSD</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Culture and language process in GSD</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Venture <input type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	Title of document: Software Ecosystems Risks Author(s): Ekananta Manalif, Luiz Fernando Capretz and Danny Ho Publication date: Source:
Infomation from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	GSD challenges/problems: The standardized process model, development coordination and management, requirement engineering, and quality assurance. Approach challenges/problems: The standardized process model, development coordination and management, requirement engineering, and quality assurance.
Infomation from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.
Infomation from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Infomation from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:
Infomation from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	Title of document: Software Product Lines, Global Development and Ecosystems: Collaboration in Software Engineering Author(s): J. Bosch, P. Bosch-Sijtsema Publication date: Source:
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	GSD challenges/problems: trends that increase complexity of dependencies between software development teams and organizations. Approach challenges/problems: trends that increase complexity of dependencies between software development teams and organizations.
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: SPIIMM: Toward a Model for Software Process Improvement Implementation and Management in Global Software Development Author(s): Arif Ali Khan, Fazal-e-Amin, Jacky Keung, M. Abdullah-Al-Wadud Publication date: 2017 Source: IEEE Access</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Quality of GSD projects Approach challenges/problems: Quality of GSD projects</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - SPIIMM <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: Validation was performed through 3 case studies in different companies, and by means of a questionnaire for feedback from the experts.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Student Research Abstract: A Framework for assisting Software Process Improvement program in Global Software Development</p> <p>Author(s): Arif Ali Khan</p> <p>Publication date: 2016</p> <p>Source:</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Software Process Improvement (SPI)</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems:Software Process Improvement (SPI)</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p>() YES</p> <p>(x) NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p>() YES</p> <p>(x) NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Systematic literature review and empirical investigation of barriers to process improvement in global software development: Client–vendor perspective</p> <p>Author(s): Arif Ali Khanuma, Jacky Keunguma, Mahmood Niazi, Shahid Hussainuma, Awais Ahmad</p> <p>Publication date: 07/2017</p> <p>Source: Information and Software Technology</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: software process improvement</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: software process improvement</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: Validation was done using survey questionnaires.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Systematic literature study for dimensional classification of success factors affecting process improvement in global software development: client–vendor perspective</p> <p>Author(s): Arif Ali Khan, Jacky Keung, Shahid Hussain, Mahmood Niazi, Suzanne Kieffer</p> <p>Publication date: 08/2018</p> <p>Source: IET Software</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Software process process improvement (SPI)</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Software process process improvement (SPI)</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p>() YES</p> <p>(x) NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p>() YES</p> <p>(x) NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Systematic review of success factors and barriers for software process improvement in global software development</p> <p>Author(s): Arif Ali KhanJacky Keung</p> <p>Publication date: 10/2016</p> <p>Source: IET Software</p>
<p>Information from RQ1</p> <p>What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?</p>	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Develop SPI practices for distributed environments, build relationships between distributed organizations, overcome temporal distance, and address cultural aspects.</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Develop SPI practices for distributed environments, build relationships between distributed organizations, overcome temporal distance, and address cultural aspects.</p>
<p>Information from RQ2:</p> <p>How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?</p>	Through systematic review and study on the subject.
<p>Information from RQ3:</p> <p>The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
<p>Information from RQ4:</p> <p>The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
<p>Information from RQ5:</p> <p>How was the proposal/approach evaluated?</p>	Evaluation description: Validation will take place in future work

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Task Environment Complexity, Global Team Dispersion, Process Capabilities, and Coordination in Software Development Author(s): Gwanhoo Lee, William Delone, J. Alberto Espinosa Publication date: 12/2013 Source: IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Geographic location, time zone, culture and organization and management Approach challenges/problems: Geographic location, time zone, culture and organization and management</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: Various forms of validation were used, such as guidelines recommended by Petter et al. [90] to validate the construct validity of the formative measures. And the multi-trace-multi-method matrix analysis modified (MTMM) proposed by Loch et al. [91] to validate the convergent and discriminant validity of formative measures.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	Title of document: The Impact of Global Software Cultural and Linguistic Aspects on Global Software Development Process (GSD): Issues and Challenges Author(s): Sameer Abufardeh, Kenneth Magel Publication date: Source:
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	GSD challenges/problems: Impact of culture and linguistic on the GSD Approach challenges/problems: Impact of culture and linguistic on the GSD
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	through systematic review
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: No data to evaluate

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Tools to Support Global Software Development Processes: A Survey Author(s): Javier Portillo-Rodríguez, Aurora Vizcaíno, Christof Ebert, Mario Piattini Publication date: 08/2010 Source: 2010 5th IEEE International Conference Global Software Engineering (ICGSE)</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Distance factor (temporal, geographical, cultural and linguistic distance) Approach challenges/problems: Distance factor (temporal, geographical, cultural and linguistic distance)</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject.
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - They present a lot of tools to support GSD, for example: IBM Rational DOORS, eRequirements, Rational Requirements Composer <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

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Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Towards a hypothetical framework of humans related success factors for process improvement in global software development: systematic review Author(s): Arif Ali Khan, Mahmood Niazi, Jacky Keung, Shahid Hussain Publication date: 03/04/2017 Source: SAC 2017: Symposium on Applied Computing</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Software Process Improvement (SPI) Approach challenges/problems: Software Process Improvement (SPI)</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	<p>through systematic review</p>
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Proposes a hypothetical framework for implementing SPI <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: Empirical validation is planned for future work</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Methodological Support for Coordinating Tasks in Global Product Software Engineering Author(s): Carolus B. Widiyatmoko, Sietse J. Overbeek, Sjaak Brinkkemper Publication date: 2017 Source: On the Move to Meaningful Internet Systems. OTM 2017 Conferences</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Communication and project control problems that can decrease the overall performance of the organization. Approach challenges/problems: Communication and project control problems that can decrease the overall performance of the organization.</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	through systematic review
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - Method Association Approach <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	<p>Evaluation description: For validation, researchers and practitioners were invited to get feedback from a broader perspective, as well as from real users. In addition, two constructs from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) were used: Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use.</p>

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	<p>Title of document: Understanding the functions of teleconferences for coordinating global software development projects: Teleconferences function for coordinating GSD</p> <p>Author(s): Gamel O. Wiredu</p> <p>Publication date: 03/2011</p> <p>Source: Information Systems Journal</p>
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	<p>GSD challenges/problems: Organizational challenges</p> <p>Approach challenges/problems: Organizational challenges</p>
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	I suppose it is through systematic review and study on the subject
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES - MeetRoom</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>Artifacts whose provenance was extracted:</p> <p>Form of provenance data storage:</p> <p>Provenance Analysis method:</p>
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.

Information Type	Data
Reference Information:	Title of document: Using distributed agile patterns for supporting the requirements engineering process Author(s): J. Bosch, P. Bosch-Sijtsema Publication date: Source:
Information from RQ1 What are the challenges or problems of GSD presented?	GSD challenges/problems: Problems of in effective collaboration Approach challenges/problems: Problems of in effective collaboration
Information from RQ2: How were these challenges and problems defined / discovered?	Based on action research
Information from RQ3: The proposal/approach use some tool / software to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO
Information from RQ4: The proposal/approach use some provenance model to support the GSD?	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO Artifacts whose provenance was extracted: Form of provenance data storage: Provenance Analysis method:
Information from RQ5: How was the proposal/approach evaluated?	Evaluation description: They didn't mention it.